

ACDTree: a bioinformatics toolkit to support the development and long-term sustainability of pathogen genomic surveillance workflows

Verónica Mixão¹, Joana Pereira¹, Miguel Pinto¹, Joana Isidro¹, João Paulo Gomes¹ and Vítor Borges^{1*}

¹Genomics and Bioinformatics Unit, Department of Infectious Diseases, National Institute of Health Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), Lisbon, Portugal

*Corresponding author: Vítor Borges (vitor.borges@insa.min-saude.pt)

Abstract

Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS) has revolutionized infectious disease surveillance, providing high-resolution data for outbreak detection, insights into pathogen population structure, and improved public health decision-making. In bacteria, core- and whole-genome Multilocus Sequence Typing (cg/wgMLST) has become a standard typing approach, but its development, implementation, and ongoing maintenance remain challenging and variable across laboratories, undermining comparability and coordination of genomic surveillance at both national and international levels.

To address these challenges, we present the first implementation of ACDTree, an open-source bioinformatics toolkit comprising three complementary tools (EvalTree, DownTree, and PanTree) designed to support key stages across the life-cycle of a genomic surveillance workflow, in strong interoperability with ReporTree. EvalTree enables systematic workflow benchmarking by assessing clustering behavior, stability and congruence, thus supporting pipeline design, validation and inter-laboratory comparability. DownTree facilitates the selection of representative genomes from large datasets, assisting cg/wgMLST schema development and scalable routine analyses. PanTree gathers information about locus diversity, prevalence and presence/absence profile in a species tree, enabling the rational selection of loci for wgMLST implementation.

In summary, ACDTree is a modular, pathogen-agnostic toolkit that streamlines genome selection, schema design, and comparative performance assessments of genome-scale typing workflows, thus supporting their deployment and long-term sustainability, as well as inter-laboratory pipeline comparability.

Keywords: typing workflows; genomic surveillance; outbreak detection; cluster congruence; cg/wgMLST

1. Motivation

The advent and steep increase in the application of Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS) worldwide has transformed infectious disease surveillance, enabling more precise outbreak tracking, deeper insights into population structure, and better-informed public health decision-making [1,2]. Nowadays, multiple approaches are available for WGS data analysis in genomic surveillance, differing in resolution, scalability, analytical focus, and accommodating the different characteristics of each species [3]. For instance, in the bacterial field, core-genome (cg) and whole-genome (wg) Multilocus Sequence Typing (MLST) have become standard typing approaches, offering high discriminatory power for efficient genomic surveillance [3–6]. Nevertheless, the application of cg/wgMLST and other WGS-based surveillance workflows remains insufficiently harmonised and varies considerably across laboratories, including differences in species-specific cg/wgMLST schemas and in the software used for key steps, such as allele calling and cluster detection [4]. Furthermore, rapid developments in bioinformatics require continuous workflows' maintenance and optimization, incorporating state-of-the-art software and updated parameters. As a result, this inter-laboratory variability can undermine the comparability of results and hinder effective cooperation and communication for outbreak detection and investigation at both national and international levels. In this context, for example, for cg/wgMLST workflows to be effective: i) schemas must accurately capture the full species diversity, while providing sufficient discriminatory power to distinguish closely related strains; ii) their design and implementation should rely on evidence-informed decisions about resolution and suitability for surveillance goals, particularly in comparison with other available solutions; iii) their software updates maintain consistency in clustering results, supporting reproducibility and reliable outbreak detection; and, finally, iv) a good knowledge of inter-laboratory pipeline comparability is essential to enable coordinated surveillance efforts at international and intersectoral levels, contributing to an efficient One Health surveillance [4,7,8]. Although recent efforts are being made to standardize and improve specific components of the workflows, there is still a need for bioinformatics solutions that support the full life cycle of a pathogen genomic workflow, from schema development to systematic inter-laboratory comparison of clustering outputs.

To address these ongoing challenges, we provide a brief introduction to the design and first implementation of ACDTree, a comprehensive, open-source toolkit composed by three complementary components (EvalTree, DownTree and PanTree) which together facilitate representative genome selection, workflow optimization and cluster comparability, in interoperability with the automated detection and characterization of genetic clusters provided by ReporTree [9]. Finally, we also discuss the potential application of each one of the tools

beyond their original purpose, widening their utility as independent tools to further improve genomic surveillance workflows, and delve into future developments and perspectives.

2. Implementation

ACDTree is an easy-to-use toolkit designed to support the development, implementation, and long-term sustainability of genome-scale typing workflows for pathogen surveillance (e.g., cg/wgMLST), being openly available on GitHub licensed under the permissive GNU General Public License (GPLv3): <https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ACDTree>. As described below, ACDTree comprises three different python-based tools, namely, EvalTree, DownTree and PanTree, which were carefully designed to seamlessly work with ReporTree [9], taking advantage of its ability to determine and report genetic clusters at all possible resolution levels. This compatibility allows the extension of ACDTree scope to different workflow types (e.g., cgMLST- or SNP-based analyses) and clustering strategies, including single-linkage hierarchical clustering or minimum-spanning tree-based approaches.

2.1 EvalTree

Purpose

A major challenge during both the development and long-term maintenance of genomics workflows lies in systematically characterizing their performance relative to alternative approaches, as well as quantifying the impact of software updates or methodological modifications over time. EvalTree is a flexible command-line tool for assessing the congruence between the classification results obtained by different typing methods/approaches, thus enabling the rapid and standardized execution of key tasks throughout the entire life cycle of a (newly developed) genome-scale typing workflow, including: i) evaluation of clustering behavior across all possible threshold levels; ii) assessment of its clustering congruence with species population structure and historical traditional typing data; iii) comparative performance analysis against other WGS-based typing workflows (e.g., newly developed cg/wgMLST schemas or previously implemented genome-scale typing systems); and iv) fine-scale comparative evaluation its comparative performance in the identification of potential outbreak-related isolates. Together, these functionalities support evidence-based optimization, benchmarking, and validation of genome-scale typing strategies for pathogen surveillance.

Design

EvalTree was designed to evaluate the comparability between two typing solutions (traditional and/or genome-scale), automating a previously developed methodology, which, through

pairwise comparisons of clustering results (e.g., obtained with ReporTree [9]), allows inferring the congruence between traditional and/or WGS-based typing methods at any or all resolution levels [4]. To this end, this methodology uses a previously developed tool (“ComparingPartitions”, <http://www.comparingpartitions.info/>) that was refined by our group (*comparing_partitions_v2.py*, available at <https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ComparingPartitions>), now being able to calculate the Adjusted Rand (AR) and the Adjusted Wallace (AWC) coefficients (among others) between any two typing classifications [10], including cg/wgMLST, and being fully compatible with ReporTree’s [9] outputs, allowing the comparison of:

- a. the clustering obtained at progressively increasing distance thresholds of a genome-scale typing method, by determining the neighborhood Adjusted Wallace coefficient (nAWC) at consecutive partitions:

$$nAWC = AWC_{n+1} \rightarrow AWC_n$$

- b. the clustering obtained at all possible resolution levels between two typing methods, independently of whether they are WGS-based or traditional, combining the AWC between methods A and B (in both directions) and the AR into a Congruence Score (CS) of each comparison, which varies from 0 (no congruence) to 3 (absolute congruence):

$$CS = AWC_{A \rightarrow B} + AWC_{B \rightarrow A} + AR$$

While “a” allows the identification of stability regions [11], *i.e.*, subsequent distance thresholds providing similar clustering results, “b” allows the determination of the congruence between any two genome-scale workflows or between a genome-scale workflow and species population structure or traditional typing data. Regarding this last point, EvalTree not only outputs the metrics and the CS obtained in each pairwise comparison, but also provides the inter-pipeline corresponding points, *i.e.*, the threshold of one pipeline that provides the most similar clustering results in the other, assessed as the highest CS above a user-defined minimum score. When a given threshold has a single valid corresponding point, this is assumed as the point of highest congruence. When a given threshold has several valid corresponding points (*i.e.*, the highest CS was found in multiple comparisons), the closest threshold is reported as the best match. Furthermore, EvalTree processes the information regarding the inter-pipeline corresponding points and determines the trend line fitting their distribution, as well as the respective r^2 and slope. This information can be used as a proxy to evaluate whether two genome-scale typing workflows yield highly concordant clustering at the exact same level, with slopes close to 1 (*i.e.*, $y = x$ scenario) reflecting high clustering

concordance and similar discriminatory power across all levels. To also assess how the discriminatory power of two genome-scale workflows compares at high-resolution thresholds, EvalTree analyses the cluster composition information provided by ReporTree [9] and determines the number of clusters identified by a given workflow at a user-defined threshold that are also detected, with the exact same composition, by another workflow at a (or up to a) similar or even higher user-defined threshold. Clusters with overlapping samples but different compositions are considered as different clusters. For an easy-to-explore interpretation and interactive visualization of all these results, EvalTree generates a summary report in HTML format, thus leveraging a user-friendly service.

Input/output

EvalTree accepts as input tab-delimited files with typing/clustering information at one (traditional typing) or multiple (e.g., cg/wgMLST typing) resolution levels, and provides different argument options that can be used to tailor the analysis according to the scientific question. Among these arguments, we highlight the possibility of adjusting the settings that are used to define cluster stability regions (minimum AWC and size of the threshold range) or defining the minimum CS to determine inter-pipeline corresponding points. Noteworthy, instead of tab-delimited files, EvalTree can accept as input the output folder of a ReporTree [9] run. In this case, EvalTree takes advantage not only of the clustering determined at all threshold levels for one or the two genome-scale workflows under comparison, but also of other information that allows performing an in-depth comparison at outbreak-level (as described above). With a single command line, this tool generates multiple output files in tabular format with detailed information about the CS obtained at each comparison, the exact coordinates of the inferred cluster stability regions, or even the outbreak-level clusters determined by each typing workflow. In order to facilitate the interpretation of the results by the user, EvalTree outputs also include an interactive HTML report with visualization modules powered by Plotly [12]. To facilitate its installation, a conda environment file is provided in GitHub (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ACDTree/tree/main/EvalTree>), together with the open-source code. Furthermore, EvalTree is available for standalone installation and deployment though conda (<https://anaconda.org/insapathogenomics/evaltree>) and PyPi (<https://pypi.org/project/evaltree/>) packages.

2.2 DownTree

Purpose

A common challenge in pathogen genomics and evolutionary studies is the selection of genome assembly datasets that represent the genetic diversity of a given lineage or species.

This step is especially critical for applications such as cg/wgMLST schema creation, where the choice of representative genomes directly determines its discriminatory power and ability to capture the genetic diversity of the species, thereby ensuring broad applicability. DownTree addresses this need by enabling the systematic selection of representative, high-quality assemblies from large and diverse datasets, integrating genetic clustering information with assembly quality metrics. As expected, the added value of DownTree increases proportionally with the volume and diversity of genomic data available for a given species, where manual curation becomes impractical and standardized, reproducible selection strategies are essential.

Design

DownTree was designed to streamline the selection of a representative subset of high-quality genome assemblies from a large and diverse dataset, ensuring that the retained subset captures the underlying genetic diversity. This selection process is guided by genetic clustering patterns and assembly quality metrics and can be performed by:

- a. Defining a target number of genome assemblies (n). In this option, DownTree infers the typing variable (corresponding to a threshold level in the genome-scale clustering analysis) that, taking into consideration the maximum number of representative assemblies to be selected per typing group (s), allows the selection of a number of assemblies that is the closest to n .
- b. Defining the typing variable (corresponding to a threshold level in the genome-scale clustering analysis) that should be used as a proxy for species diversity, independently of the number of genome assemblies selected.

Notably, DownTree can be run in “evaluation mode”, which allows the users to preview the expected selection outcomes and take informed decisions regarding the options set. Of note, to ensure that most diversity is represented in the selected subset, when the input typing information corresponds to genome-scale clustering at subsequent distance thresholds (e.g., ReporTree [9] partitions table, *i.e.* tab-delimited file with clustering information at all possible levels), DownTree selects the most divergent high-quality assemblies of a cluster as its representatives.

Input/Output

DownTree accepts as input a tab-delimited file with typing/clustering information at one (e.g., traditional typing) or multiple (e.g., existing genome-scale solutions) resolution levels and a

tab-delimited file with assembly metrics, providing different argument options that can be used to tailor the analysis according to the specific needs. These options include not only the definition of the assembly metric that should be taken as a proxy for assembly quality (and the respective quality threshold), but also the possibility of defining the maximum number of representative assemblies to be selected per typing group (s).

With a single command line, this tool generates two output files, namely: i) a detailed table indicating, for each typing group, which are the selected representatives or, if no isolates passed the assembly quality threshold and the input corresponded to genome-scale clustering, at which level of resolution it belongs to a cluster with selected representatives; and ii) an updated version of the provided assembly metrics table with indication of whether a sample was selected as representative of a typing group or whether it is part of a typing group with selected representatives. To facilitate its installation, a conda environment file is provided in GitHub (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ACDTree/tree/main/DownTree>), together with the open-source code.

2.3 PanTree

Purpose

Another challenge, and particularly relevant for cg/wgMLST workflows, depending on the population structure and pangenome diversity of the target species, is determining whether a wgMLST schema (core plus accessory loci) is required to enhance isolate discrimination. PanTree addresses this challenge by evaluating locus prevalence and allele diversity and mapping their distribution onto a “species” tree topology. This enables informed decisions regarding the inclusion or exclusion of accessory loci in a new wgMLST schema. Indeed, for some bacterial species, implementing a wgMLST schema - rather than the conventional cgMLST - can be essential to achieve sufficient resolution for isolate discrimination during outbreak detection and investigation [13,14].

Design

PanTree was designed to evaluate wgMLST loci prevalence and allele diversity in a large dataset, and map their presence/absence in the “species” tree topology, providing evidence for an informed decision on the inclusion of loci in cg/wgMLST schemas. Based on this information, PanTree assesses not only the loci prevalence and diversity in the whole dataset used (e.g. determined with DownTree), but also for each cluster detected at all grouping variables (corresponding to threshold levels if a cgMLST clustering table is provided, e.g., generated with ReporTree [9]) defined by the user. Additionally, based on a user-defined

threshold for cluster prevalence, *i.e.*, number of typing groups or cgMLST-determined clusters in which a given locus is detected at a certain typing group/level, PanTree flags the loci that should be kept or removed from the cg/wgMLST schema under evaluation.

Input/Output

PanTree accepts as input a tab-delimited file with allelic profiles, a tab-delimited file with typing information (from traditional typing or existing genome-scale solutions) and a phylogenetic tree/dendrogram (e.g., generated with ReporTree [9]). With a single command line, this tool outputs not only a tab-delimited file for each threshold level set by the user with information about loci prevalence per cluster, but also a summary table combining this information with loci diversity and prevalence across the whole species tree together with the indication of whether a loci passes or not the criteria defined by the user to be maintained in the cg/wgMLST schema. Moreover, a heatmap generated with seaborn [15] is output showing the loci prevalence/absence across the species tree. To facilitate its installation, a conda environment file is provided in GitHub (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ACDTree/tree/main/PanTree>), together with the open-source code.

3. Potential Applications and Future Perspectives

ACDTree was designed with the objective of serving as a suite of interoperable, pathogen-agnostic bioinformatics tools to support and streamline the development and long-term sustainability of genomic surveillance workflows, being available in GitHub (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ACDTree>) as open-source software. Seamlessly integrated with ReporTree [9], its first implementation is specially advanced and refined for bacterial workflows relying on cg/wgMLST-based typing approaches, thus ensuring scalability, flexibility, and data-driven decision-making throughout the entire life-cycle of a cg/wgMLST workflow. Indeed, ACDTree tools offer key functionalities: DownTree facilitates the selection of diverse and high-quality genome representatives from a large dataset, PanTree guides schema extension with biologically informed metrics, and EvalTree supports workflow performance assessment, benchmarking and validation. While DownTree and PanTree tackle specific needs of cg/wgMLST workflow development, EvalTree has a much broader utility, playing a pivotal role not only during genome-scale workflow development, but also during its implementation and continuous maintenance by: i) supporting developers during new cg/wgMLST schema construction (e.g., providing information about the congruence between the clustering patterns obtained with a genome-scale workflow and the pathogen population structure or traditional typing data); ii) supporting decision-making during new laboratory

implementations by comparing the performance of the workflow to its peers; and, iii) providing a rapid way to control the effect of upcoming software updates.

Beyond its primary target of facilitating the implementation of end-to-end cg/wgMLST genomic surveillance and outbreak investigation, the individual ACDTree components can address additional challenges routinely faced by pathogen genomic surveillance and research teams. For instance, DownTree can also be easily used for selecting high-quality genomes that represent specific population groups (e.g., sequence types, serotypes, etc.) or for selecting a representative genome of each cluster identified at a given threshold (e.g., outbreak level), among other parallel applications. These capabilities are increasingly valuable as we transition into the Big Data era, with some bacterial species being represented by hundreds of thousands of genomes in public databases - a number that continues to grow. From a public health perspective, following the detection of potential outbreaks using cg/wgMLST, in-depth investigation still typically progresses to SNP-based analyses to increase discriminatory power [3]. In this context, DownTree's ability to rapidly identify high-quality representative genomes for all clusters identified potential outbreak level across large collections can help streamline and partially automate routine SNP-based investigations - a step that remains a gap in the field, as SNP analysis are often context-specific, manual and not easily scalable to large datasets or bioinformatics platforms. Possible future developments of DownTree include expanding the tool to directly accept genome assemblies as input, enabling the internal calculation of assembly quality metrics, and to use multiple metrics during assembly selection. This would make the process more streamlined, autonomous, and user-friendly.

Regarding PanTree, this new tool supports the exploration of wgMLST schema designs that go beyond the core genome, promoting the rational inclusion of accessory loci towards increased resolution and in-depth genomic characterization. With special relevance for bacterial species with open and highly diverse pan-genome, PanTree can support future studies assessing whether the use of wgMLST in routine surveillance - for example, through a dynamic wgMLST approach that performs cluster "zoom-in" by automatically incorporating shared accessory loci (as implemented in ReporTree [9]) - can achieve levels of resolution close to the maximum, as those traditionally obtained through the intra-outbreak SNP-based approaches. Beyond this primary purpose, PanTree can also support broader research applications. For instance, it can help identify loci whose presence/absence patterns align with the phylogenetic structure, which may be useful for pinpointing genes potentially associated with lineage-specific phenotypic traits, such as virulence determinants that have emerged and stabilized within specific branches of the phylogeny or even resistance genes predominantly found in particular clonal lineages. Possible future developments of PanTree include

expanding it with interactive output visualization formats, as well as incorporating new analytical and statistical modules capable of processing phenotypic metadata to streamline the detection of loci with phylogenetic signal that might be associated with clinically relevant traits, such as antimicrobial resistance or host adaptation.

Besides the need-driven development of DownTree and PanTree, a main focus of ACDTree development was directed towards EvalTree. Indeed, this tool addresses multiple relevant questions by comparing cluster compositions at all possible allele threshold levels between workflows or typing tools. Specifically, it: i) characterizes the clustering behavior of each workflow, identifying “stability regions”, which is crucial for pathogen nomenclature design; ii) measures cluster congruence at all resolution levels between two WGS-based workflows or between a WGS-based workflow and traditional typing methods; and iii) evaluates and compares workflow performance in detecting similar outbreak signals. EvalTree culminates in an interactive user-friendly HTML report that facilitates the easy exploration and interpretation of results, promoting transparency and reproducibility. In public health settings, these versatile functionalities can be translated into various applications that extend beyond the development of new cg/wgMLST schemas. Indeed, EvalTree functionalities can contribute to advance the inter-laboratory comparability, standardization, and reproducibility required by international organizations, such as the World Health Organization (WHO), the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) [8,16]. Demonstrating this added-value, the methodology behind EvalTree already proved essential for a multi-country and intersectorial assessment of clustering congruence between workflows for genomic surveillance of foodborne pathogens [4]. By automating large-scale comparative analyses and generating interpretable outputs, EvalTree addresses limitations of typical exercises for inter-laboratory comparability assessment (e.g., External Quality Assessments, ring trials, proficient tests, etc.), which are usually focused on outbreak cluster detection among a limited number of isolates, and which need to evolve to another scale in terms of dataset size and diversity, as well as of magnitude of congruence assessment [4]. Indeed, given the vast panoply of bioinformatics workflows available and the constant development/refinement of new/existing solutions, EvalTree can contribute to overcome the existing doubt on the comparability of their results, which has hindered optimal WGS-based outbreak case definition [4,17,18]. As public health agencies worldwide continue adopting WGS for routine surveillance, toolkits like ACDTree can contribute to ensuring inter-laboratory comparability, high-resolution monitoring and outbreak response at global scale, being totally aligned with the growing need for tools that enable global, One Health-compatible genomic surveillance.

In summary, by integrating EvalTree, DownTree and PanTree, ACDTree provides a comprehensive and versatile toolkit to support the development, deployment, evaluation, and long-term sustainability of pathogen genomic surveillance workflows. It facilitates the transition from traditional to WGS-based typing by enabling informed dataset selection, biologically guided schema development, cluster comparability assessment, and continuous intra-laboratory performance evaluation. Beyond supporting the creation and refinement of new workflows, ACDTree also promotes large-scale inter-laboratory comparability assessments, extending far beyond conventional EQA or ring trials in terms of dataset size and diversity, and ultimately offers end-to-end support for genomic surveillance and outbreak investigation, accelerating the implementation of genomics-informed public health action for bacteria X and beyond.

Funding

This work was supported by the ISIDORE project (funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme, Grant Agreement no. 101046133) and by the European Union project "Sustainable use and integration of enhanced infrastructure into routine genome-based surveillance and outbreak investigation activities in Portugal" - GENE0 [101113460] on behalf of the EU4H programme [EU4H-2022-DGA-MS-IBA-01-02]. This work was also supported by DURABLE "Research Network against Epidemics" project co-funded by The European Commission Union under the EU4Health Programme (EU4H) [101102733 to V.B.]. However, views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible. VM contribution was supported by national funds through the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), I.P., in the frame of Individual CEEC 2022.00851.CEECIND/CP1748/CT0001 (doi: 10.54499/2022.00851.CEECIND/CP1748/CT0001). JP contribution was supported by national funds through FCT, I.P., in the frame of the Project "MycoSurveil" (grant number 2023.12824.PEX; doi: 10.54499/2023.12824.PEX).

References

1. Gomes E, Araújo D, Nogueira T, Oliveira R, Silva S, Oliveira LVN, et al. Advances in whole genome sequencing for foodborne pathogens: implications for clinical infectious disease surveillance and public health. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.* 2025;15:1593219. doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2025.1593219
2. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. Expert opinion on whole genome sequencing for public health surveillance. ECDC, editor. Stockholm; 2016. Available from: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/media/en/publications/Publications/whole-genome-sequencing-for-public-health-surveillance.pdf>
3. Uelze L, Grützke J, Borowiak M, Hammerl JA, Juraschek K, Deneke C, et al. Typing methods based on whole genome sequencing data. *One Health Outlook.* 2020;2:3. doi: 10.1186/s42522-020-0010-1
4. Mixão V, Pinto M, Brendebach H, Sobral D, Dourado Santos J, Radomski N, et al. Multi-country and intersectoral assessment of cluster congruence between pipelines for genomics surveillance of foodborne pathogens. *Nat Commun.* 2025;16(1):3961. doi: 10.1038/s41467-025-59246-8.
5. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Costa G, Di Piazza G, Koevoets P, Iacono G, Liebana E, et al. Guidelines for reporting Whole Genome Sequencing- based typing data through the EFSA One Health WGS System. *EFSA Support Publ.* 2022;19. Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7413>
6. Nadon C, Van Walle I, Gerner-Smidt P, Campos J, Chinen I, Concepcion-Acevedo J, et al. PulseNet International: Vision for the implementation of whole genome sequencing (WGS) for global food-borne disease surveillance. *Euro Surveill.* 2017;22 (23):30544. doi: 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2017.22.23.30544
7. Forth LF, Malorny B, Bönn M, Brinks E, Denay G, Deneke C, et al. An inter-laboratory study characterizes the impact of bioinformatic approaches on genome-based cluster detection for foodborne bacterial pathogens. *Front Microbiol.* 2025;16:1629731. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2025.1629731
8. World Health Organization. Whole genome sequencing as a tool to strengthen foodborne

disease surveillance and response. Module 2: whole genome sequencing in foodborne disease outbreak investigations. World Health Organization; 2023. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/server/api/core/bitstreams/c0328129-7de9-4b48-819d-baf43c2b021e/content>

9. Mixão V, Pinto M, Sobral D, Di Pasquale A, Gomes JP, Borges V. ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data. *Genome Med.* 2023;15:43. doi: 10.1186/s13073-023-01196-1

10. Carriço JA, Silva-Costa C, Melo-Cristino J, Pinto FR, de Lencastre H, Almeida JS, et al. Illustration of a common framework for relating multiple typing methods by application to macrolide-resistant *Streptococcus pyogenes*. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2006;44:2524–32. doi: 10.1128/JCM.02536-05

11. Barker DOR, Carriço JA, Kruczkiewicz P, Palma F, Rossi M, Taboada EN. Rapid identification of stable clusters in bacterial populations using the adjusted Wallace coefficient. *bioRxiv*; 2018. Available from: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/299347>

12. Sievert C. Interactive Web-based Data Visualization with R, Plotly, and Shiny. CRC Press; 2020.

13. Leeper MM, Tolar BM, Griswold T, Vidyaprakash E, Hise KB, Williams GM, et al. Evaluation of whole and core genome multilocus sequence typing allele schemes for outbreak detection in a national surveillance network, PulseNet USA. *Front Microbiol.* 2023;14:1254777. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1254777

14. Llarena A-K, Ribeiro-Gonçalves BF, Nuno Silva D, Halkilahti J, Machado MP, Da Silva MS, et al. INNUENDO: A cross- sectoral platform for the integration of genomics in the surveillance of food- borne pathogens. EFSA supporting publication. 2018;EN-1498:142. Doi: 10.2903/sp.efsa.2018.EN-1498

15. Waskom M. seaborn: statistical data visualization. *J Open Source Softw.* 2021;6:3021.

16. European Centre for Disease Control (ECDC), Van Walle I, Guerra B, Borges V, André Carriço J, Cochrane G, et al. EFSA and ECDC technical report on the collection and analysis of whole genome sequencing data from food- borne pathogens and other relevant microorganisms isolated from human, animal, food, feed and food/feed environmental

samples in the joint ECDC- EFSA molecular typing database. EFSA Support Publ [Internet]. 2019;16. Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1337>

17. Michelacci V, Asséré A, Cacciò S, Cavaiuolo M, Mooijman K, Morabito S, et al. European Union Reference Laboratories support the National food, feed and veterinary Reference Laboratories with rolling out whole genome sequencing in Europe. *Microb Genom.* 2023;9(7):mgen001074. doi: 10.1099/mgen.0.001074

18. Struelens MJ, Ludden C, Werner G, Sintchenko V, Jokelainen P, Ip M. Real-time genomic surveillance for enhanced control of infectious diseases and antimicrobial resistance. *Front Sci* [Internet]. 2024; 2:1298248. doi: 10.3389/fsci.2024.1298248